

Hydride generation technique in flame atomic absorption spectrometry : Determination of antimony in the presence of thorium matrix

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Manuscript received 7 August 2006, accepted 21 August 2006

Abstract : A method has been developed for the determination of Sb in the presence of thorium matrix, using hydride generation technique in Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrometry with air-acetylene as oxidant fuel combination. Studies have been carried out in detail to obtain the maximum absorbance signal due to the formation of Sb hydride in presence of thorium matrix. The efficiency of which is normally governed by the factors such as oxidant-fuel flow rate, KI concentration, hydrochloric acid molarity and concentration of thorium matrix. This has led to the determination of antimony to a level as low as 0.4 ppm on thorium basis using 5 mg/ml Th matrix. Analysis of synthetic samples revealed a good agreement between the estimates obtained with those of added amounts with a precision better than 5% RSD. It is of significance to note that the present method gains its uniqueness for its ability to determine the analyte without the need for a prior chemical separation of a matrix as complex as Th.

Keywords : Thorium matrix, antimony, hydride, AAS.

India's nuclear power programme envisages the use of thorium on a large scale by converting it into fissile material in Fast Breeder Reactor (FBR) and also as a nuclear fuel material in Advance Heavy Water Reactors (AHWRs). Trace metal assay forms an important aspect of chemical characterization of thorium. Antimony is one such element specified by fuel fabricators. The determination of Sb in thorium matrix was reported¹ using Electro-Thermal Atomization Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (ETA-AAS) wherein absorbance signal of antimony was found to be affected in proportion to an increase in the amount of thorium present in the sample, resulting its determination at 0.8 ppm in 2.5 mg/ml of thorium. Though the determination of analytes in presence of various matrices such as Th^{1,2}, U³ and Pu^{4,5} is reported using ETA-AAS, the application of hydride generation technique, however, in presence of these matrices is not yet investigated in detail⁶. Use of hydride generation technique for determination of Sb has been reported in water⁷, plant materials⁸, beer and wort⁹, soils and vegetables¹⁰ and drugs¹¹. A recent publication¹² has critically reviewed the mechanism of generation of volatile hydrides and the formation of analyte atoms in the quartz cell for hydride forming elements in AAS.

The main advantage of analytical methods involving hydride generation technique lies in the achievement of

physical separation of the matrix thereby leading to improved sensitivity. The present investigations mainly emphasized the study on the effect of thorium matrix on the efficiency of hydride generation and so as to develop a sensitive and precise method for its determination using hydride generation flame atomic absorption spectrometry.

Results and discussion

Various factors affecting the hydride generation efficiency of antimony in presence of thorium, such as KI concentration, reaction time, acid molarity, and the flame parameters were studied in detail. Absorbance measurements were carried out both in absence as well as in presence of Th matrix. Optimization of gas-flow parameters was carried out using Sb 20 ng/ml in aqueous solution wherein oxidant flow was kept constant as 10 L/min while varying the acetylene flow in the range 1.47 to 1.59 L/min. Maximum signal could be attained at 1.53 L/min C₂H₂ flow which was henceforth used in further investigations (Table 1).

The efficiency of hydride generation process depends to a greater extent on the valence state of the Sb ions present in the solution. The technique being most sensitive to detect Sb in its trivalent state, hence, there is a need to reduce all Sb^V in the sample to Sb^{III} prior to hydride generation. This is reported to be achieved, by

Table 1. Effect of C_2H_2 flow on absorbance signal

Sl. no.	Flow rate (L/min)	Absorbance
1.	1.47	0.185
2.	1.50	0.180
3.	1.53	0.250
4.	1.56	0.145
5.	1.59	0.147

pre-treating the sample/standard solutions with excess of KI¹³. Though, KI, is known to be used as a reducing agent for Sb; the reactivity of Sb with KI was likely to get affected due to the presence of Th in the present studies. This was checked by varying the concentration of KI in the solutions containing 10, 20 and 50 ng/ml of Sb, in aqueous solutions as well as in the presence of 5 mg/ml Th matrix. The concentration dependent absorbance signals for Sb were measured in the range 20–400 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of KI. The results for 20 ng Sb in both the matrices are presented in Table 2. As can be seen from the table, the absorbance was found to increase upto 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration of KI, beyond which it remained unaffected in both aqueous as also in Th matrix thereby indicating that presence of Th in the solution did not affect the reduction reaction for Sb.

Table 2. Effect of KI concentration on Sb absorbance

Sl. no.	Concentration of KI ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance	
		Aqueous	Thorium
1.	Without KI	0.072	0.075
2.	20	0.185	0.190
3.	50	0.250	0.245
4.	100	0.240	0.250
5.	200	0.245	0.240
6.	300	0.250	0.250
7.	400	0.252	0.245

Studies were carried out to ascertain the time required for completion of the reduction reaction and also to investigate the effect of prolonged storage, by following the absorbance signal as a function of time. For this purpose 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of KI was added to the solutions, containing 50 ng/ml of Sb, and the absorbance measurements were carried out at time intervals of 5 min to 30 h. To check the stability of solution over a period of time, absorbance were measured for the same solution after three, five and seven days. Graphical representation of these results is shown in Fig. 1. Results indicated that conver-

Fig. 1. Effect of time on storage.

sion of Sb^{V} to Sb^{III} was almost complete within 15 min and the absorbance remained stable up to twenty four hours within the limit of variation. However, after seven days the signal got reduced by 50% as compared to that obtained earlier on completion of reduction reaction. It can be inferred from these results that KI initially reduces Sb^{V} to Sb^{III} accompanied by the release of I_2 (essentially an oxidizing agent), which remains in the solution. Over a period of time I_2 present in the solution oxidizes Sb^{III} to Sb^{V} , resulting in reduced absorbance signal. These studies revealed that fresh preparation of standards and samples are essential before the analysis. Similar experiments were carried out in the presence of 5 mg/ml of thorium matrix. There was no change in absorbance value, as well as time required for the completion of reduction reaction even in the presence of Th matrix.

Investigations were carried out to study the influence of HCl on the signal sensitivity by varying its concentration in the range 0.5–4.0 M. The results are shown in Table 3. As seen from the table, the molarity of the acid plays a significant role in improving the absorbance signal. With increasing acid concentration the absorbance signal increased up to 3 M; thereafter it was found to be stable. The formation of HI, in presence of KI and HCl, which effectively reduces Sb^{V} to Sb^{III} , was probably optimum at this acid concentration. Hence, further studies were carried out in 3 M acid concentration.

Table 3. Effect of acid concentration on Sb signal

Sl. no.	HCl concentration (M)	Absorbance
1.	0.5	0.05
2.	1.0	0.05
3.	1.5	0.10
4.	2.0	0.185
5.	3.0	0.250
6.	4.0	0.252

As can be seen, from the experiments carried out to study the effects of KI concentration, acid molarity and storage time, Th does not have any direct effect on analyte absorbance. Based on these results it can be inferred that gaseous thorium hydride is not formed under the present conditions. As a result Th remained in solution, which prevented its transportation to the absorption cell. The influence of Th concentration on 20 ng/ml Sb signal was examined to monitor the tolerance of Th in the sample solution so as to obtain the best relative sensitivity for its determination. The effect was studied, with varying concentration of Th in the range 1–20 mg/ml in 3 M HCl with prior addition of 50 µg/ml KI. Blank contribution from Th on the analyte absorbance was also checked in the same concentration range as above which was found to be negligible for the entire range of concentration of Th. However, the analyte signals measured in presence of Th reveals that the signal intensity for Sb remains unaffected with increasing Th concentration up to 10 mg/ml. The results are shown in Table 4. It was observed that the nozzle of the sample pump tube was blocked after feeding solutions containing 20 mg/ml thorium. Hence the apparent decrease in the absorbance signal was attributed to the reduction in sample uptake due to the blocked nozzle on feeding the large amount of dissolved solids. Therefore, to avoid problems associated with sample uptake, thorium concentration was restricted to 5 mg/ml, which provided adequate improvement in the detection sensitivity.

Table 4. Effect of Th concentration

Sl. no.	Th concentration (mg/ml)	Absorbance
1.	1	0.210
2.	2	0.219
3.	5	0.220
4.	10	0.213
5.	20	0.095

In light of the above studies, the relative performance of the analytical technique have been carefully examined and useful analytical range, lowest amount determined in solution and sensitivity of the method as evaluated from the slope of analytical curve both in absence as well as in presence of thorium is given in Table 5. The analytical ranges were found to be linear between 2.0 and 70 ng/ml in both the matrices. The relative detection limit at 0.4 ppm, obtained as µg/g basis will depend on the matrix concentration, which in the present case, is 5 mg/ml of Th. Three synthetic samples in 5 mg/ml thorium were analyzed using the standardized procedure. These results are shown in Table 6, which indicates a good agreement between the estimates obtained with those of added concentration. The precision of the determinations calculated using different sample at 5, 20 and 30 ng/ml concentration with ten replicate measurements was found to be better than 5% RSD. The method can successfully be employed for the determination of Sb in presence of Th matrix.

The method developed here, is unique in its ability to determine the analyte without the need for chemical separation from a matrix like thorium. Presence of Th matrix

Table 5. Optimized experimental parameters and figure of merits

Sl. no.	Parameters used	
1.	Wave length	271.6 nm
2.	Flow rates :	
	Oxidant	10.0 L/min
	Fuel	1.53 L/min
3.	HCl concentration	3.0 M
4.	KI concentration	50.0 µg/ml
5.	Th concentration	5.0 mg/ml
6.	Range of analysis :	
	Aqueous	2.0–70 ng/ml
	Thorium (5 mg/ml)	2.0–70 ng/ml
7.	Lowest amount determined :	
	Aqueous	2.0 ppb
	5 mg/ml Thorium	0.4 ppm
8.	Sensitivity	0.0134 Abs/ng

Table 6. Analysis results of synthetic samples in Th matrix

Sl. no.	Amount added (ng/ml)	Amount determined (ng/ml)	RSD (%)
1.	5.0	6.0	±5.0
2.	20.0	22.0	±3.0
3.	30.0	28.5	±4.0

up to 10 mg/ml did not affect the absorbance signal for Sb. Though use of KI improved the absorbance signal, over the period of time the signal was found to reduce, thus requiring fresh preparation of standards and samples each time. The method can successfully be used for the determination of Sb in 5 mg/ml thorium matrix. Using this concentration, the specification limit for Sb in Th can easily be achieved.

Experimental

Apparatus :

A GBC-906 Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS) equipped with HG 3000 Hydride Generation accessory, was used in the present studies. Single elemental Hollow Cathode Lamp (HCL) was used for Sb and a deuterium lamp with sampling frequency of 200 Hz was used for background correction. Signal measurements were carried out in signal integration mode. Metal hydride formed in the reaction vessel was carried to the quartz absorption cell placed on premixed slot type air-C₂H₂ burner and were dissociated in the flame heated quartz tube. Argon was used to carry the analyte hydride in to the hydride cell through the gas-liquid separator. Air-C₂H₂ flame was used to dissociate the hydride and to form analyte atoms.

High purity Sb and ThO₂ were used to prepare the elemental stock solutions. Quartz double distilled water was used for the dilutions of standards and samples. All other chemicals like HCl, HNO₃, HF, KI, NaOH and NaBH₄ were of analytical grade.

Preparation of standards and samples : Stock solution of Sb was prepared at 2 mg/ml concentration using high purity Sb metal. Required amount of metal powder was weighed, dissolved in aqua-regia and evaporated to dryness, redissolved in concentrated HCl and dried. The process was repeated six times for conversion to antimony chloride and to remove nitrate ions. Finally the residue was dissolved in 3 M HCl. Weighed amount of thorium oxide was dissolved in HNO₃ + HF mixture (HF 0.01 M), evaporated to near dryness and re-dissolved in hydrochloric acid. The process was repeated six times to remove traces of nitrate and fluoride and convert it to chloride. Finally it was made upto 200 mg/ml in 3 M HCl. KI solution was prepared at 10 mg/ml concentration by weighing and dissolving the appropriate amount of KI. Two sets of standards were prepared from the

analyte stock solution in the range 1.0 to 100 ng/ml in 3 M HCl media with and without the addition of thorium matrix. Further a series of solutions were prepared with Sb at 20 ng/ml and varying Th concentration in the range 1–20 mg/ml. Three synthetic samples were prepared and analyzed by adding known amounts of Sb in 5 mg/ml of thorium solution. All the dilutions were made with 3 M HCl. Standards and samples were treated with 50.0 µg/ml of KI prior to their use.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Dr. V. K. Manchanda, Head, Radiochemistry Division, for his constant encouragement during the course of this work.

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